

Elucidation of electrochemical reduction behavior of dinitro group containing pesticides Chlornidine, Dipropalin and Prodiamine residues in soil, water and agricultural formulations

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Abstract : An electroanalytical technique has introduced for the elucidation of reduction behaviour of dinitro group containing pesticides such as Chlornidine, Dipropalin and Prodiamine by DPAd stripping voltammetry on a hanging mercury drop electrode and cyclic voltammetry in universal buffer as supporting electrolyte. The best adsorption conditions were found to the reduction of dinitro group pesticides Chlornidine, Dipropalin and Prodiamine at pH 2.0, 4.0 and 6.0, and an accumulation potential varied from -0.65 V, -0.60 V and -0.745 V with an accumulation time of 60 s, 40 s and 50 s respectively. The effect of stirring rate, scan rate, pulse amplitude and purge time were examined for the optimization of instrumental conditions and observed linearity range at hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) with a lower detection limit 1.94×10^{-6} M, 1.821×10^{-6} M and 4.522×10^{-6} M respectively for selected pesticides. The average recoveries obtained for Chlornidine, Dipropalin and Prodiamine in soil and water samples ranged from 99.1 to 99.9%. The technique has been adequately applied to the elucidation of Chlornidine, Dipropalin and Prodiamine in soil, water and green gram samples around Srikalahasthi (Thottambedu and B. N. Kandriga mandal) agricultural regions, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Keywords : Chlornidine, Dipropalin, Prodiamine, soil and water samples, agricultural formulations, HMDE and DPAd stripping voltammetry.

Introduction

Nitro group containing pesticides are commonly used as pre- and post-budding weed control agents (herbicides) for a various types of crops, as a result, they are observed in river water¹⁻⁵, ground water^{6,7} and soils⁸⁻¹⁰. Dinitro compounds were reported to exhibit significant anti-proliferative and anti-infective activities against protozoan parasites including Leishmania species^{11,12}. Trypanosome broucei¹³ and the intraerythrocytic forms of Plasmodium falciparum¹⁴. Several analytical techniques were developed in which mostly chromatographic techniques¹⁵⁻¹⁷ for the determination of the herbicide in various soil, crops, oil seeds and water samples. These are HPLC-UV¹⁸⁻²¹, GC-ECD^{22,23} and square wave voltammetry (SWV)²⁴⁻²⁶. Fuyu Guan *et al.*²⁷ was used SPME to separate dinitro group herbicides from formulations and vegetables. Brown *et al.*²⁸ evaluated the herbicides from pumpkin (cucurbita species). Singh *et al.*²⁹

described the effect of pre-emergence herbicides on the symbiotic parameters and seed yield of soybean. Timothy Grey *et al.*^{30,31} reported the tolerances of cucurbits to the herbicides.

Current methods for the analysis of pesticides containing nitro group compounds involve either liquid-liquid extraction³², solid-phase extraction (SPE)³³ or supercritical fluid extraction (SCFE) and solid phase micro extraction³⁴ (SPME). The main disadvantages of these methods were use of large quantities are often toxic and not eco-friendly solvents, the elaborate cleaning up time-consuming procedures and the need for concentration of analytes before analysis^{35,36}.

In the present study, elucidation of electrochemical reduction behaviour of dinitro group containing pesticides at hanging mercury dropping electrode was discussed and the dinitroaniline herbicides "Chlornidine, Dipropalin and

Prodiamine" were selected as dinitro group containing pesticides.

For the elucidation of electrochemical reduction behaviour of above said dinitro group containing pesticides, cyclic voltammetry, differential pulse polarography, millicoulometry and controlled potential electrolysis were successfully employed and the results were reported in this chapter.

Experimental

The purity of the three pesticides was tested by thin layer chromatography and melting point determinations. All dilute solutions from the stock solution were prepared at that moment every time. Reagents were used for the overall process are AR grade.

From the stock solution, various concentrations were made on dilution method and labeled properly. 10 mL (1 mL known concentrated chlornidine solution and 9 mL of universal buffer solution) of electroactive solution was transferred into a 100 mL of measuring flask, to this 50 mL of 1 M KCl solution and 2.5 mL of 0.2% gelatin solution were added. This was diluted up to the mark. From this 10 mL of the solution was transferred into voltammetric cell and then deaerated with nitrogen gas for ten minutes. After the voltammogram was taken, the process was repeated for different known concentrated solutions at various pH values under optimum conditions. To the overall experiment optimum temperature was chosen as 25 °C.

The soil sample, water sample and green grams were collected from Thottambedu Mandal area, Chittoor Dist., Andhra Pradesh, India for the analysis and application of the chlornidine and dipropalin.

From the collected soil sample, all the rock particles and foreign dust particles were picked out. The soil was dried and separated into several parts, each part contain 50 g which were used for electroanalytical studies. On the thin layer of the soil sample, calculated amount of pesticide solution was sprayed properly and the pesticide sprayed soil sample part was transferred into a container. The soil sample kept constantly at room temperature on the bench in laboratory for 30 days and then the sample was recollected by DMF. The recollected solution was used for electroanalytical studies.

Different known concentration selected pesticide solution were added to the 50 mL water samples separately

and kept constant for 40 days at room temperature on the bench in laboratory and then used for the electroanalytical studies of the pesticide.

Green grams were grinded as powder and separated those into several parts of 50 g each. Known amount of pesticide was added to the aliquots of green grams appropriate weighed samples separately and kept constant for 60 days.

After the period for which sample kept constant, the mixture was extracted with 20 ml of DMF for three times. The solvent evaporated to around 1 mL and was dissolved in DMF and subjected to voltammetric studies separately for every pesticide sample. By means of standard addition method the quantity of pesticide was estimated.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical reduction activities of chlornidine, dipropalin and prodiamine were observed throughout the pH range 2.0–12.0 by differential pulse adsorptive stripping voltammetry and cyclic voltammetry. For all the said pesticides, one cathodic peak was attributed in the scan of cyclic voltammetry which evidenced the formation of cation as a reactive intermediate. In alkali medium, no well defined peaks were observed due to the less availability of protons in alkali medium and precipitations were also developed in the electroactive solution.

The electrochemical reduction studies of chlornidine, dipropalin and prodiamine found that they underwent diffusion controlled and adsorption free reduction process. The studies were also evidenced from the linear plots of I_p vs $V^{1/2}$ and I_d vs $V^{1/2}$, straight line was passing through the origin. The studies were also evidenced from the plots of current vs pH, current vs E_{acc} and current vs t_{acc} . The log plot analytical studies indicating the electrochemical reduction reactions of chlornidine, dipropalin, and prodiamine were irreversible. Millicoulometry technique was employed for the determination of number of electrons involved in the electrochemical reduction behaviour of chlornidine, dipropalin and prodiamine and also found that eight electrons are involved in the reduction process.

Electrolysis of the electroactive substances of chlornidine, dipropalin, and prodiamine was carried out at -0.65 V, -0.60 V and -0.745 V vs SCE respectively, and the products formed after the controlled potential electrolysis were identified and confirmed by the IR spec-

trum. The IR spectrum of reduced clornidine had shown -OH (-NHOH) stretch at 3550 cm^{-1} and no stretch at 1550 cm^{-1} region which was belong to the dinitro group of chlornidine.

IR spectral data of reduced dipropalin shown absence of -NO_2 stretch at $1560\text{--}1510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and found -OH (-NHOH) stretch at 3550 cm^{-1} region and IR spectral data of prodiamine shows absence of -NO_2 stretch at $1560\text{--}1510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and found -OH (-NHOH) stretch at 3550 cm^{-1} region. Halogen stretch was also found at 860 cm^{-1} which belong to the fluorine and primary amine stretch at 3250 cm^{-1} .

Kinetic parameters such as diffusion coefficient, transfer coefficient and heterogeneous forward rate constant values were evaluated based on the differential pulse adsorptive stripping voltammograms (Fig. 1) and from the cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Typical differential pulse adsorptive stripping voltammogram of chlornidine at HMDE; concentration : $3.104 \times 10^{-6}\text{ M}$; accumulation time : 40 s; scan rate : 50 mV s^{-1} ; pulse amplitude : 40 mV.

Fig. 2. Typical CV of chlornidine at pH 2.0; concentration : $3.104 \times 10^{-6}\text{ M}$; accumulation potential : -0.65 V ; accumulation time : 40 s; scan rate : 50 mV s^{-1} ; pulse amplitude : 40 mV.

Fig. 3. Typical CV of dipropalin at pH 2.0; concentration : $3.155 \times 10^{-6}\text{ M}$; rest time : 2 s; accumulation time : 60 s; scan rate : 50 mV s^{-1} ; pulse amplitude : 60 mV.

Fig. 4. Typical CV of prodiamine at pH 2.0; concentration : $2.854 \times 10^{-6}\text{ M}$; accumulation time : 50 s; scan rate : 60 mV s^{-1} ; pulse amplitude : 60 mV.

According to the sensitive voltammetric study of chlornidine at the optimum temperature $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the optimum conditions were determined for $3.104 \times 10^{-6}\text{ M}$ chlornidine were t_{acc} : 40 s; E_{acc} : -0.65 V ; scan rate : 50 mV s^{-1} and pulse amplitude : 40 mV.

Well resolvable and reproducible peak obtained for chlornidine was useful for the analysis of chlornidine in spiked soil, water and green gram (moong dal) samples. The optimum pH to get well defined peak for the detection was found to be 2.0. The peak current was found to vary linearly with the concentration of the pesticide over the range $1.0 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M}$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-9}\text{ M}$. The lower detection limit was found to be $1.94 \times 10^{-6}\text{ M}$.

In the voltammetric studies, the optimum conditions for recording a maximum developed and sharper DP-AdSV peak for $3.55 \times 10^{-6}\text{ mol L}^{-1}$ dipropalin were t_{acc} : 60 s, E_{acc} : -0.60 V , scan rate : 50 mV s^{-1} and pulse

amplitude : 60 mV, optimum temperature : 25 °C. The optimum pH to get well defined peak for the detection is found to be 6.0. The peak current is found to vary linearly with the concentration of the pesticide over the range $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-9} M$. The lower detection limit was found to be $1.821 \times 10^{-6} M$.

The optimum conditions for recording a maximum sharper DP-AdSV peak for $2.854 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ prodiamine were $t_{\text{acc}} : 50 \text{ s}$, $E_{\text{acc}} : -0.745 \text{ V}$, scan rate : 60 mV s^{-1} and pulse amplitude : 60 mV, and optimum temperature : 25 °C. The peak current is found to differ linearly with the concentration of the pesticide over the range $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-9} M$. The lower detection limit was found to be $4.522 \times 10^{-8} M$. The average recoveries obtained for chlornidine, dipropalin and prodiamine in soil, water and green grams samples were more than 90% and results were shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The recoveries of chlornidine, dipropalin and prodiamine in soil, water and green grams samples

Pesticide	Sample application	Average recovery (%)	Average standard deviation	Average relative standard deviation (%)
Chlornidine	Soil sample	99.37	0.9897	0.445
	Water sample	99.56	0.6895	0.307
	Green gram sample	99.43	0.8662	0.403
Dipropalin	Soil sample	99.54	0.0674	0.329
	Water sample	99.64	0.0533	0.255
	Green gram sample	99.68	0.0462	0.227
Prodiamine	Soil sample	99.95	0.0192	0.037
	Water sample	99.97	0.0105	0.018
	Green gram sample	99.91	0.0297	0.060

Conclusion

In the present investigation, both standard addition and calibration methods were applied for the determination of these pesticides in agricultural, water and soil samples. From the recoveries it has been observed that the proposed method described the successful application of electroanalytical techniques for analysis of these pesticides. It also demonstrates that DP-AdSV at HMDE can be conveniently used for the quantitative determination of these pesticides in above described experimental conditions. Hence, the method proposed is good and may

become an attractive alternative to chromatographic techniques which are more tedious, costly and time taking.

References

- H. Kobayashi, K. Ohyama, N. Tomiyama, O. Jimbo, O. Matano and S. Got, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1993, **643**, 197.
- D. Barcelo, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1993, **643**, 117.
- W. E. Pereira and C. E. Rostad, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1990, **24**, 1400.
- N. Yugandhar Sreedhar and K. Reddy Samatha, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1998, **72**, 247.
- R. Frank and L. I. Logan, *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 1998, **17**, 741.
- W. E. Preiera, C. E. Rostad and Th. J. Leiker, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **228**, 69.
- K. A. Caldwell, V. M. S. Ramanujan, Z. Cai and M. L. Cross, *Anal. Chem.*, 1993, **65**, 2372.
- T. S. Steinhelmer, R. L. Pfeiffer and K. D. Scoggin, *Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **66**, 645.
- S. Durand, R. Forteza and D. Barcelo, *Chromatographia*, 1989, **28**, 597.
- G. Durand and D. Barcelo, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1991, **243**, 259.
- M. M. Chan and D. Frong, *Science*, 1990, **249**, 924.
- M. M. Chan, J. Tzeng, T. J. Emge, C. T. Ho and D. Fong, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1993, **37**, 1909.
- M. M. Chan, J. Tzeng, T. J. Emge, C. T. Ho and D. Fong, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1993, **37**, 5657.
- J. Nath and I. Schneider, *Clin. Res.*, 1992, **40**, 331A.
- D. D. Shackelford, R. W. McCormick, S. D. West and L. G. Turner, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2000, **48**, 4422.
- P. Cabras and M. Melis, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1991, **585**, 164.
- A. E. Smith, L. A. Kerr and B. Caldwell, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1997, **45**, 1473.
- I. Liska, E. R. Brouwer, A. G. L. Ostheimer, H. Lingeman, U. A. T. Brinkman, R. B. Geerdink and W. H. Mulder, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1992, **47**, 267.
- A. Di Corcia and M. Marchetti, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1992, **26**, 66.
- E. A. Hogendorn, C. E. Goewise and P. van Zooneen, *Fresens. J. Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **339**, 348.
- P. R. Loconto and J. Lig, *Chormatogra*, 1991, **14**, 1297.
- J. L. Bernal, M. J. DelNozal, J. Atienza and J. J. Jimenez, *Chromatographia*, 1992, **33**, 67.
- G. Nagan and T. Ikesaki, *J. Chromatogra*, 1991, **385**, 537.

24. L. Ramaley and M. S. Krause (Jr.), *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 1362.
25. S. A. Borman, *Anal. Chem.*, 1985, **54**, 698A.
26. M. A. Lovric and S. K. Lovric, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1988, **248**, 239.
27. F. Guan, K. Watanabe, A. Ishii, H. Seno, T. Kumazawa, H. Hattori and O. Suzuki, *J. Chromatogr. (B)*, 1998, **714**, 205.
28. D. Brown and J. Masiunas, *Weed Technology*, 2002, **16**, 282.
29. H. Singh, J. K. Singh and R. P. Gupta, *Int. J. Trop. Agric.*, 1995, **13**, 143.
30. T. L. Grey, D. C. Bridges and D. S. NeSmith, *Hort Science*, 2000, **35**, 632.
31. T. L. Grey, D. C. Bridges and D. S. NeSmith, *Hort Science*, 2000, **35**, 637.
32. J. E. Patrick, (1998), Ontario Ministry of Agriculture and Food, September (1990).
33. W. E. Johnson, N. J. Fendinger and J. R. Plimmer, *Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **63**, 1510.
34. A. Dicorcia, R. Samperi, A. Marcomini and S. Stelluto, *Anal. Chem.*, 1993, **65**, 907.
35. J. C. Molto, Y. Pico, G. Font and J. Manes, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1991, **555**, 137.
36. Robert B. L. Vanliev and Linda D. Cherry, *Fundamental & Applied Toxicology*, 1998, **2**, 664.